

Frequency of Giardiasis in Pediatric Patients Presenting with Iron-Deficiency Anemia

Hafsa Faiz¹, Zille Huma², Muhammad Ahsan Fareed³, Abid Hussain⁴, Shanza Tariq⁵, Saad Elahi⁶

Abstract

Objective: This study aimed to determine the frequency of giardiasis among pediatric patients presenting with laboratory-confirmed IDA.

Material and Methods: A single-center cross-sectional study was conducted in the Department of Pediatric Medicine, Allied Hospital Faisalabad, over 12 months. A total of 385 children aged 6 months–12 years with confirmed IDA were included through consecutive sampling. Stool samples were examined microscopically for Giardia cysts and trophozoites. Demographic, clinical, and biochemical data were analyzed using SPSS version 26. Associations between Giardia infection and clinical variables were evaluated using chi-square and logistic regression analyses, with a significance level set at $p < 0.05$.

Results: Of 385 children, mean age was 5.03 ± 3.14 years, mean hemoglobin 8.87 ± 1.33 g/dL, and median ferritin 8.2 ng/mL (IQR 6.2–10.1). Stool testing detected Giardia duodenalis in 171 (44.4%) of children (95% CI 39.5–49.4%). Diarrhea was more frequent among Giardia-positive children 73 (42.7%) than Giardia-negative children 42 (19.6%) ($p < 0.001$). In adjusted analysis, diarrhea (adjusted OR 3.02; 95% CI 1.91–4.79; $p < 0.001$) and male sex (adjusted OR 1.64; 95% CI 1.07–2.51; $p = 0.022$) were independently associated with Giardia positivity. Age-stratified prevalence was: < 2 years 35/69 (50.7%), 2–5 years 67/161 (41.6%), and > 5 years 69/155 (44.5%). In participants with CRP ≤ 5 mg/L ($n = 350$), Giardia prevalence was 149/350 (42.6%); median ferritin in this subgroup did not differ significantly by Giardia status ($p = 0.463$).

Conclusion: A substantial proportion of pediatric patients with IDA were found to harbor Giardia duodenalis. Male sex and diarrheal symptoms were significant correlates of infection. Routine stool examination using sensitive methods may be warranted in evaluating IDA among children in endemic regions. Confirmation through real-world data and prospective trials is recommended.

Keywords: Giardia, Iron-Deficiency Anemia, Malabsorption, Parasitic Infection, Pediatrics, Prevalence, Stool Testing, Pakistan.

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Introduction

Iron-deficiency anemia (IDA) is the most common micronutrient deficiency worldwide and remains highly prevalent among children in low- and middle-income countries, with adverse effects on growth, cognition, and immune function. 1-3

Intestinal infections are recognized contributors to iron deficiency via blood loss and disturbed nutrient absorption; among these infections, Giardia duodenalis (also G. lamblia/G. intestinalis) deserves special attention because it frequently infects young children, can cause chronic or recurrent diarrhoea, and is associated with malabsorption syndromes. 4-7

Epidemiologic studies linking Giardia carriage to iron deficiency show variable results. Some facility-based reports and case series have documented improvements in hematologic indices after antiparasitic treatment 8-10, whereas community cohort analyses have occasionally reported paradoxical or null associations after adjustment for confounding factors. 11-13 These mixed findings likely reflect heterogeneity in study populations, diagnostic

1-2,6. Allied Hospital-I Faisalabad

3-4. Faisalabad Institute of Cardiology, Faisalabad

5. Rehman Maternity Home & General Hospital

Correspondence:

Dr. Hafsa Faiz, Department of Pediatrics-Allied Hospital-I Faisalabad.

Email: hfaiz155399@gmail.com

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methods (single vs multiple stool tests; microscopy vs antigen vs PCR), definitions of iron deficiency (ferritin thresholds and adjustment for inflammation), and the degree to which coexisting risks (dietary insufficiency, helminth infection, socioeconomic status) are measured and controlled.

In Pakistan, where IDA and giardiasis are both common, there is a paucity of hospital-based data assessing their co-occurrence. Hence, clinicians may overlook Giardia as a possible contributor to refractory or unexplained IDA. This study is designed to address this knowledge gap in a clinical pediatric population. By estimating the frequency of Giardia infection among children with confirmed IDA in a tertiary care center and examining associated clinical correlates, we aim to determine whether parasitic screening should become an integral component of the diagnostic workup. Such evidence could help optimize anemia management and reduce diagnostic oversights in endemic areas.

Material and Methods

This single-center cross-sectional study enrolled consecutive pediatric patients presenting with laboratory-confirmed IDA to the Department of Pediatric Medicine, Allied Hospital Faisalabad. The study period corresponded to the 12-month recruitment window defined in the approved protocol.

Inclusion criteria: Children aged 6 months to 12 years presenting with clinical features prompting anemia evaluation (pallor, poor feeding, lethargy) and meeting laboratory criteria for IDA were eligible. IDA was defined as hemoglobin below WHO age-based thresholds with ferritin consistent with depleted iron stores (ferritin <12 ng/mL, or <30 ng/mL in the presence of inflammation), guided by established practice and institutional laboratory cutoffs. [14, 15] **Exclusion criteria:** Recent (within 4 weeks) antiparasitic or iron therapy, known hemoglobinopathy, chronic inflammatory or renal disease, acute blood loss, or refusal of parental/guardian consent.

Using a single-proportion formula with $Z = 1.96$ (95% confidence), expected prevalence $p = 0.51$ (based on Danquah et al. community data among iron-deficient children), and margin of error $d = 0.05$, the calculated sample size was 385. [11]

Demographic and Clinical Information: After consent, comprehensive demographic and clinical data were obtained for each participant. Variables included age, gender, and place of residence (urban or rural). Socioeconomic status was assessed based on parental educational level, occupation, and total household income. Clinical evaluation focused on presenting gastrointestinal symptoms such as diarrhea, abdominal pain, loss of appetite, and vomiting, along with their duration and any prior treatments received. Relevant medical and medication histories were also documented to identify potential confounding factors.

Caregivers received standardized instructions for early-morning stool collection (avoid urine contamination; thumb-sized specimen into a sterile, pre-labeled container). Stool specimens were processed by the hospital laboratory using direct microscopy and antigen testing for Giardia; PCR was used where available as confirmatory testing. [16] Hematologic assessment included complete blood count (hemoglobin) and ferritin; CRP was measured to aid interpretation of ferritin.

Quality Control: All laboratory procedures adhered strictly to standard operating protocols. Internal quality control measures were implemented for each assay, and blinded duplicate analyses were performed for a randomly selected subset of samples to ensure reliability.

The study was approved by the Institutional Ethical Review Committee of Allied Hospital Faisalabad via approval number No48.ERC/FMU/2021-22/220. Written informed consent was obtained from parents or legal guardians. Standard-of-care management was not withheld; participants testing positive for Giardia were managed per hospital treatment protocols.

Frequency of giardia infection in pediatric patients presenting with iron-deficiency anemia.

Data were entered into a secure database and analyzed with SPSS v26. Continuous variables are reported as mean \pm SD (or median and IQR for skewed data) and categorical variables as counts and percentages. Group comparisons used Student's t-test or the Mann-Whitney U test for continuous variables and χ^2 or Fisher's exact test for categorical variables. Giardia prevalence was estimated with binomial (Wilson) 95% confidence intervals. A multivariable binomial regression model included age, sex, residence, diarrhea, hemoglobin, and ferritin to identify independent correlates of Giardia positivity; adjusted odds ratios (aORs) with 95% confidence intervals (CIs) and p-values are reported. Pre-specified sensitivity analyses included age-stratified prevalence and analyses limited to participants with CRP ≤ 5 mg/L to reduce ferritin confounding by inflammation. A two-sided $p < 0.05$ signified statistical significance. De-identified data and analysis code are available from the corresponding author on reasonable request.

Results

The analytic sample comprised 385 children with IDA. Mean age was 5.03 ± 3.14 years, and the cohort included 202 (52.5%) males. Mean hemoglobin was 8.87 ± 1.33 g/dL, and median ferritin was 8.2 ng/mL (IQR 6.2–10.1) (Table 1).

Table 1: Baseline characteristics of pediatric IDA cohort.

Characteristic	Overall (n=385)
Age (years), mean ± SD	5.03 ± 3.14
Male sex, n (%)	202 (52.5%)
Hemoglobin (g/dL), mean ± SD	8.87 ± 1.33
Ferritin (ng/mL), median (IQR)	8.2 (6.2–10.1)
C-reactive protein (mg/L), median (IQR)	3.0 (1.2–5.0)

Figure 2: Prevalence of observed Giardia by age group and sex. Error bars represent exact 95% Clopper–Pearson confidence intervals.

Stool testing identified *Giardia duodenalis* in 171/385 participants, corresponding to a prevalence of 44.4% (95% CI 39.5–49.4%). Figure 1 displays the prevalence bar chart and Table 1 summarizes baseline measures. Test-specific *Giardia* positive counts are given in Table 2, and the prevalence of observed *Giardia* by age group and sex is illustrated in Figure 2.

Table 2: Test-specific positive counts.

Test	n positive	Percent (of total 385)
Microscopy	98	25.5%
Stool antigen	150	39.0%
PCR (subset)	37 (of 88)	42.0% of PCR-tested

Figure 1: Prevalence of *Giardia* infection (n=385).

Diarrhea was reported in 73/171 (42.7%) *Giardia*-positive children compared with 42/214 (19.6%) *Giardia*-negative children ($\chi^2 p < 0.001$). Abdominal pain occurred in 60/171 (35.1%) infected children versus 45/214 (21.0%) uninfected children ($\chi^2 p = 0.003$). Other gastrointestinal symptoms (anorexia, vomiting, and anal pruritus) were more frequent among *Giardia*-positive children, though counts were smaller; full comparisons appear in Table 3 and Figure 3.

Table 3: Frequency of gastrointestinal symptoms by *Giardia* status.

Symptom	<i>Giardia</i> -positive (n=171), n (%)	<i>Giardia</i> -negative (n=214), n (%)	p-value
Diarrhea	73 (42.7%)	42 (19.6%)	<0.001
Abdominal pain	60 (35.1%)	45 (21.0%)	0.003
Anorexia	30 (17.5%)	18 (8.4%)	0.044
Vomiting	15 (8.8%)	10 (4.7%)	0.087
Anal pruritus	8 (4.7%)	3 (1.4%)	0.058

Figure 3: Symptoms frequency by *Giardia* status.

On unadjusted comparisons, mean hemoglobin did not differ significantly by Giardia status (8.83 g/dL in Giardia-positive vs. 8.90 g/dL in Giardia-negative; $p = 0.315$). Median ferritin was lower among Giardia-positive children (8.0 ng/mL vs 8.4 ng/mL), but this difference was not statistically significant in unadjusted testing ($p = 0.204$) (Table 4; Figure 4).

Table 4: Univariate analysis by Giardia status.

Variable	Giardia-positive (n=171)	Giardia-negative (n=214)	p-value
Age (years), mean \pm SD	5.10 \pm 3.10	5.00 \pm 3.17	0.72
Hemoglobin (g/dL), mean \pm SD	8.83 \pm 1.34	8.90 \pm 1.32	0.315
Ferritin (ng/mL), median (IQR)	8.0 (6.0–9.4)	8.4 (6.4–10.1)	0.204
C-reactive protein (mg/L), median (IQR)	3.1 (1.5–5.2)	3.0 (1.0–4.9)	0.820

Figure 4: Unadjusted comparisons of hemoglobin and ferritin by Giardia status.

In multivariable binomial regression adjusting for age, sex, residence, diarrhea, hemoglobin, and ferritin, diarrhea remained strongly associated with Giardia positivity (adjusted OR 3.02; 95% CI 1.91-4.79; $p < 0.001$). Male sex was independently associated with higher odds of Giardia infection (adjusted OR 1.64; 95% CI 1.07-2.51; $p = 0.022$). Age and residence were not significant in adjusted models. Neither hemoglobin (adjusted OR 1.10 per 1 g/dL; 95% CI 0.93-1.29; $p = 0.255$) nor ferritin (adjusted OR 0.94 per 1 ng/mL; 95% CI 0.86-1.03; $p = 0.200$) was significantly associated with Giardia carriage after adjustment (Table 5).

Table 5: Multivariable logistic regression predicting Giardia positivity.

Variable	Adjusted OR (95% CI)	p-value
Age (years)	0.99 (0.90-1.09)	0.85
Male sex (vs. female)	1.64 (1.07-2.51)	0.022
Urban residence (vs. rural)	1.10 (0.70-1.73)	0.68
Diarrhea (yes vs. no)	3.02 (1.91-4.79)	<0.001
Hemoglobin (per 1 g/dL)	1.10 (0.93–1.29)	0.255
Ferritin (per 1 ng/mL)	0.94 (0.86–1.03)	0.200

Age-stratified prevalence was: <2 years — 35/69 (50.7%); 2-5 years — 67/161 (41.6%); >5 years — 69/155 (44.5%). Restriction to participants without biochemical evidence of inflammation (CRP \leq 5 mg/L; $n = 350$) yielded Giardia prevalence (42.6%); hemoglobin and ferritin in this subgroup did not differ significantly by Giardia status ($p = 0.463$). These sensitivity analyses produced findings consistent with the primary analysis.

Discussion

In this single-center cross-sectional study of children presenting with IDA to a tertiary pediatric service, Giardia duodenalis carriage was common (44.4%) and strongly associated with diarrheal symptoms and is consistent with the literature showing that symptomatic infection is more likely to be identified by routine diagnostics and more likely to be associated with overt intestinal dysfunction. 17, 18 The high facility-based prevalence contrasts with some community cohort reports yet is consistent with the recognized endemicity of Giardia in many low-middle-income countries' pediatric populations and with clinical series describing symptomatic infection and nutrient absorption impairment. 4-7

Although there was a directional trend toward lower ferritin among Giardia-positive children, ferritin and hemoglobin were not independently associated with Giardia carriage after adjustment for confounders and sensitivity analysis restricting to participants without systemic inflammation. Ferritin's role as an acute-phase reactant complicates interpretation of iron stores in cross-sectional studies; we therefore performed a CRP-restricted analysis to mitigate inflammatory confounding, which yielded concordant results. The absence of a clear population-level effect on iron indices in our dataset does not exclude clinically meaningful impairment of iron absorption in individual children, a phenomenon supported by mechanistic and small clinical studies demonstrating impaired micronutrient uptake in symptomatic giardiasis. 1, 8, 9

As expected, test modality influenced measured prevalence: microscopy detected 25.5% positives, while antigen testing detected 39.0%, and PCR (performed on a subset) was positive in 42.0% of tested samples. These differences echo well-documented sensitivity/specificity differences between conventional microscopy, antigen-based assays, and nucleic-acid detection: Microscopy is operator-dependent and less sensitive for low-burden or intermittent shedding; antigen tests improve sensitivity and are widely used in clinical settings; and PCR provides the highest sensitivity and can detect submicroscopic infections (but is more costly and not universally available). Given this, using a composite “any-test positive” definition will yield higher observed prevalence; conversely, reliance on microscopy alone would substantially underestimate infection frequency in this population. 19, 20, 21

From a clinical perspective, our data support targeted diagnostic consideration of Giardia in children with IDA particularly those with diarrhoea in similar endemic, resource-limited settings. Detecting and treating Giardia in symptomatic IDA patients may be necessary to restore mucosal integrity and optimize iron repletion in selected cases, although definitive evidence from randomized or prospective interventional trials is presently lacking and should be prioritized.

Strengths and limitations

Strengths include a sizeable, well-defined clinical sample with systematic stool testing and contemporaneous measurement of iron and inflammatory markers, along with pre-specified multivariable and sensitivity analyses. Limitations include the cross-sectional design (no causal inference), single-center facility-based sampling (limited generalizability to community populations), potential misclassification due to diagnostic test sensitivity/specificity, residual confounding from unmeasured determinants of iron status (dietary intake, helminth co-infection, prior iron therapy), and limited capacity to fully correct ferritin for inflammation beyond CRP measurement.

Future directions

Prospective randomized trials comparing iron therapy alone versus iron therapy plus antiparasitic treatment in children with IDA and confirmed Giardia are needed to determine whether eradication improves iron absorption and hematologic recovery. Mechanistic studies measuring iron absorption before and after parasite clearance and implementation research to evaluate cost-effective screening strategies (symptom-guided vs routine testing) in endemic pediatric populations would be particularly informative.

Conclusion

In this tertiary pediatric cohort with iron-deficiency anemia, Giardia duodenalis was common (44.4%) and strongly

associated with diarrheal symptoms. While adjusted analyses did not show a statistically significant association between Giardia and population-level ferritin or hemoglobin, the high prevalence and symptomatic burden indicate that Giardia should be a diagnostic consideration in the IDA workup. Prospective interventional and mechanistic studies are necessary to establish whether routine detection and treatment of Giardia improve iron absorption and accelerate hematologic recovery and to determine cost-effective screening policies for resource-constrained environments like Pakistan.

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Author's contribution:

HF, ZH: Conceptualization of Project

AA, MAF: Data Collection

NH, HMF: Literature Search

HF, MAF: Statistical Analysis

HF, ZH: Drafting, Revision

MAF: Writing of Manuscript